

A Five-Year Review Of Perforated Peptic Ulcer Disease in a Tertiary Hospital in Lafia, North-Central Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Perforated peptic ulcer disease is a life-threatening surgical emergency associated with high morbidity and mortality in the absence of prompt surgical intervention. **Objective:** To determine the pattern of presentation and outcome of management of perforated peptic ulcer disease patients in a tertiary hospital in Lafia, North- central Nigeria. **Methodology:** A structured questionnaire was used to extract clinico-epidemiological and outcome data of perforated peptic ulcer disease patients operated over a 5-year period. Chi- square test was used to analyze categorical variables while Mann- Whitney test was used for continuous variable analysis. Statistical significance was inferred at P-value of < 0.05. **Results:** We documented 74 patients, 69 (93.2%) males. The mean age was 38 ±12.8years and majority of the patients were farmers (43.2%). Chronic non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug use was the most common risk factor documented. Sixty-six (89.1%) patients presented after 24 hours of onset of symptoms. A total of 57(77%) patients had gastric perforations. The most common complication was surgical site infection among 29(39.2%) patients, followed by multiple organ failure, 9 (12.2%) and repair leak, 5(6.8 %). Mortality rate was 23% and was found to be more common among those patients who presented late and those with multiple organ failure. Mortality was significantly associated with age greater than 60 years (p=0.004), primary level of education (p=0.019) and post-operative complications (p=0.001). **Conclusion:** Perforated peptic ulcer accounts for high morbidity and mortality in our study and mainly affected the youths. Chronic non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug use was the dominant risk factor. Old age, primary level of education, late presentation and post-operative complications were found to increase mortality.

Keywords: Peptic ulcer disease, Perforation, Surgical site infection, Mortality.

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INTRODUCTION

Perforated peptic ulcer disease (PPUD) is a frequent complication of peptic ulcer disease (PUD) requiring urgent surgical intervention. Mortality from PUD ranges from 6.6% to 13.6% depending on how prompt and effective surgical intervention were administered.^{1,2}

Factors such as chronic use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, *Helicobacter pylori* infection, alcohol, cigarette smoking, use of steroids among others, may irritate the protective lining of the gastroduodenal epithelium which may result in ulceration and progress into perforation.

The pattern and distribution of PPUD varies from one geographical area to another and this has been attributed to the varying degrees of exposure of patients to the risk factors. In the low and middle-income countries, late presentation to health facilities is a major problem with huge consequences. This can be attributed to ignorance, poverty, fear of surgery, patronage of traditional healers among others.

At least 5% of PUD patients develop PPUD during their life time.³ The classic triad of sudden onset of abdominal pains, tachycardia and board-like rigidity is the hallmark of PPUD. The diagnosis of PPUD is mainly clinical, however, radiological imaging studies are supportive with the demonstration of air under the diaphragm. Prompt diagnosis, aggressive resuscitation and urgent surgical intervention are essential to reduction of morbidity and mortality from PPUD.

Currently, the most preferred surgical technique is Graham's omentopexy.^{4,5} Factors associated with poor prognosis includes older age, delayed presentation, presence of shock at presentation and the presence of co-morbidities.⁶

Although perforated peptic ulcer disease is a common cause of peritonitis in our sub-region, there is paucity of research in North-central Nigeria.

We conducted a descriptive, retrospective study to determine the pattern of presentation and outcome of PPUD patients managed in Lafia, North-central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This was a retrospective descriptive study of consecutive patients operated for PPUD at Dalhatu Araf Specialist Hospital (DASH), Lafia, Nasarawa state, North-central Nigeria.

Dalhatu Araf Specialist hospital is a 400 bed capacity state tertiary institution providing primary, secondary and a wide range of specialist care for patients in North-central Nigeria.

All adult patients who were operated on for PPUD from July 1, 2018 to June 30, 2023 were included in the study. Patients that were managed non-operatively, those with gastroduodenal perforations from trauma and those with incomplete or missing data were excluded.

We used a structured questionnaire to extract patient's data from their case notes in the medical records and theatre operation registers. These data included clinico-epidemiological information, results of laboratory tests, intra-operative findings, definitive surgery, morbidities and mortalities.

All data obtained for the research were subjected to statistical analysis using the statistical product and service solution (SPSS) version 23 statistical software. The results were presented as frequencies, mean and captured in tables. Chi-square test was used to analyze categorical variables while Mann-Whitney U-test was used for continuous variable analysis. Statistical significance was inferred at a P-value of < 0.05

Ethical considerations

The study was conducted after obtaining ethical clearance from the research and ethical committee of Dalhatu Araf Specialist Hospital, Lafia. Anonymity of the patients was maintained by the use of medical record numbers in the research report. Confidentiality was maintained during the period of the research.

RESULTS

During the study period, 80 patients underwent emergency laparotomy for perforated peptic ulcers; of these, 6 patients were excluded from the study due to missing data.

Seventy-four patients were therefore enrolled in the study.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics

Variable	Frequency n=74	Percent
Sex		
Male	69	93.2
Female	5	6.8
Age		
<30	21	28.4
30-39	17	23.0
40-49	17	23.0
50-59	13	17.6
≥60	6	8.0
Mean±SD	38.0±12.8	
Education		
Primary	32	43.2
Secondary	27	36.5
Tertiary	12	16.2
None	3	4.1
Occupation		
Farming	32	43.2
Traders	14	18.9
Student	9	12.2
Artisan	7	9.6
Civil servant	5	6.8
Others	7	9.5

Table 1 outlines demographic characteristics of study participants (n=74) based on sex, age, education, and occupation. The majority of the participants were male, constituting 93.2%. The mean age was 38.0±12.8 years, reflecting the average age of study participants.

Educational backgrounds vary, with 43.2% having primary education, and a smaller percentage (4.1%) having no formal education. Occupationally, study participants included individuals mainly engaged in farming (43.2%).

Table 2. Clinical history

History	Frequency	Percent
Abdominal pains	74	100.0
Constipation	41	55.4
History of dyspepsia	37	50.0
Vomiting	33	44.6
Fever	28	37.8
Abdominal distension	74	100.0

Table 2 provides insight into the prevalence of various medical histories among the participants. Abdominal pains and distension were constant symptoms in all the patients, while history of dyspepsia was present in 50.0% of participants.

Table 3. Site and size of perforation

Variable	Frequency n=74	Percent
Site		
Gastric perforation	57	77.0

Duodenal perforation	17	23.0
Size (cm)		
0.5-1.0	36	48.6
1.1- 2.0	24	32.4
2.1- 4.0	14	18.9

The majority of perforations occurred in the gastric region, accounting for 77.0% of cases, while 23.0% were identified in the duodenal region.

Table 4. Interval between onset of symptoms and presentation at the hospital and mortality

Variable	Outcome		Frequency [percentage]
	Alive	Dead	
Onset of symptoms			
0-24 hours	8	0	8 [10.8]
25-48 hours	8	2	10 [13.5]
49-72 hours	22	2	24 [32.4]
> 72 hours	19	13	32 [43.2]
	57	17	74 [100.0]

All the mortalities were recorded among patients whose symptoms were more than 24 hours prior to surgery. (Table 4)

Table 5. Association between selected characteristics and treatment outcome

Variable	Alive n=54 Freq(%)	Death n=17 Freq(%)	X ²	P-value
Sex			0.150	0.699
Male	54(78.3)	15(21.7)		
Female	3(60.0)	2(40.0)		
Age			15.594	0.004*
30	19(90.5)	2(9.5)		
30-39	14(82.4)	3(17.6)		
40-49	12(70.6)	5(29.6)		
50-59	11(84.6)	2(15.4)		
≥60	1(16.7)	5(83.3)		
Education			9.977	0.019*
Primary	21(65.6)	11(34.4)		
Secondary	21(77.8)	6(22.2)		
Tertiary	12(100.0)	0(0.0)		
None	3(100.0)	0(0.0)		

*=Statistically significant

Mortality was significantly associated with patients who were 60-years and above and those with primary level of education.

Table 6. Association between site of perforation, method of repair, morbidity and treatment outcome

Variable	Alive n=54 Freq (%)	Death n=17 Freq (%)	X ²	P-value
Site			2.497	0.114
Gastric perforation	41(71.9)	16(28.1)		
Duodenal perforation	16(94.1)	1(5.9)		
Method of repair			0.001	>0.999
Modified Grahams omentopexy	56(76.7)	17(3.3)		
Simple closure	1(1.8)	0(0.0)		
Morbidity			66.566	<0.001*
Multiple Organ Failure	0[0.0]	9[100.0]		

Repair Leak	1(25.0)	4(80.0)
Surgical site infection	28(96.6)	1(3.4)
Others	0(0.0)	3(100.0)
Nil	28(100.0)	0(0.0)

*=Statistically significant

In summary, while there is no significant association between the site of perforation or the method of repair and mortality, however, there is a significant association between the postoperative complications and mortality (Table 6).

DISCUSSION

Perforated PUD is a common cause of peritonitis among adult patients presenting to the emergency department.¹ It is a serious surgical complication of peptic ulcer disease with associated huge consequences.³ Despite advances in the diagnosis and medical treatment of peptic ulcer disease, perforated peptic ulcer still remains a major cause of concern.⁶

In this study, 74 patients with perforated peptic ulcer were operated over a 5 year period giving an average of 14.8 cases annually. This is higher than the rates reported by Nuhu, Benjamin and Olaogun *et al.* in North-eastern, South-south and South-western parts of Nigeria respectively, but lower than the 20.8 cases per annum recorded by Dongo and colleagues in another study in South-south region of Nigeria.^{4,5,6,7}

Chalya *et al.* reported a rate of 17 cases per year in Tanzania while Dakubo and co-workers reported 36

cases annually at Korle-bu Teaching Hospital in Ghana, both studies also demonstrated higher incidences of perforated PUD.^{8,9} As the risk factors for PUD is multifactorial, these geographical differences may reflect the varying rates of exposure to these risk factors.

This study showed a male predominance with a male to female ratio of 13.8 to 1. This finding is similar to several others from within Nigeria, Tanzania, Ghana and Ethiopia.^{5,8,9,10} However, it is in variance with the female preponderance reported by Thosen *et al.* in Norway.¹¹

The mean age of patients in our study was 38.0 years. This is consistent with findings from some other studies within and outside Nigeria.^{4,9} However, it is at variance with the study by Benjamin *et al.* from

South-eastern Nigeria who found a higher mean age of 44 years.⁵

Farmers and artisans constituted over 50% of the study population with either primary or secondary level of education. They are assumed to be of a low socioeconomic status due to their small scale practice. Yim and his colleagues, demonstrated an association between low level of education and low socioeconomic status with PUD.¹² This is because the level of education and socioeconomic status are related to living conditions such as hard physical work, use of pain killers, inadequate nutrition and psychological stress among others.¹² These are risks factors for PUD that may eventually become complicated with perforation.

Ohene-Yeboah and colleagues in their study at Kumasi, Ghana, showed that 47.7% of the patients with perforations were chronic non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) users.¹³ This corroborates with our findings in which the highest ranked risk factor was chronic NSAIDs usage. This is also similar to the study of Gisbert *et al.* in Madrid, Spain.¹⁴ Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs inhibits cyclo-oxygenase enzyme which is needed for the production of prostaglandins which is a gastrointestinal epithelial protective agent.

Among patients with perforated PUD, only 30% of them have a prior history of PUD at diagnosis.¹ In this study, 50% of the patients had dyspepsia, even though none had an upper gastrointestinal endoscopy to confirm the presence of peptic ulcer disease. It was expected that such patients would have taken precautionary measures with proper treatment to avert perforation but this was not the case probably from the low level of education or socioeconomic factors.

The diagnosis of perforated PUD is made based on clinical symptoms and signs, imaging studies and confirmation at surgery. This study in corroboration with other studies revealed abdominal pain as the dominant symptom.^{3,4,5,6,7,8} This was followed by constipation, vomiting and fever in the order of reduced frequency of occurrence. While the constipation and vomiting could be attributed to ileus, the presence of fever suggest a late presentation. The majority (89.1%) of patients presented after 24 hours which is similar to other studies.^{6,8} In the study by Obonna and Oribabor *et al.*, all the patients presented later than 24 hours.^{15,16}

The changing pattern of perforated PUD from the previously predominant duodenal perforation to gastric perforation was demonstrated by Egwuonwu and co-workers who were able to establish the association between the rising gastric perforation rate with increasing use of NSAIDs.¹⁷

Whereas Dongo *et al.* reported a higher perforated gastric ulcer to duodenal ulcer as was the case in this study, most of the other studies in Nigeria reported a higher perforated duodenal ulcer to gastric ulcer.^{7,18,19}

Surgery is the main treatment option for patients with peritonitis from perforated ulcer. The various surgical techniques include, Graham's omentopexy, simple closure and rarely partial gastrectomy.^{5, 6,20}

The choice of these techniques depends on the size of the perforation, extent of contamination, patients' fitness, malignant perforation and surgeon preference. In this study, majority of the patients were offered Graham's omentopexy because it is easy, fast and life-saving with low morbidity. It is also the predominant technique in all other studies.^{3,6,7}

Surgical site infection was the most common complication in this study. A rate of 39.2% is comparable to similar studies in Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa. Though all the surgeries were class IV operative wounds with infection rates as high as 40%. The high infection rate is attributable to the gross contamination at surgery. In contrast, Dakubo and co-workers at Kor-le Bu teaching hospital in Ghana recorded a higher Chest infection rate as

against surgical site infection.⁹ We could not explain this disparity. Morbidity and mortality following surgery for perforated PUD is very worrisome.

The mortality rate of 23% in our study is similar to those of Ohene-Yeboah *et al.* who reported 22.1%.¹³ Multiple organ failure accounted for majority of the deaths. Nuhu *et al.* in their research in Maiduguri, Northern-eastern Nigeria, reported a mortality rate of 55.6%, whereas, mortality rates of 40%, 17.4% and 21% were reported in South-south, South-east and South-western Nigeria respectively.^{4,5,6,19} All the mortalities in our study occurred in patients that presented after 24 hours of development of symptoms. Similar studies in Ethiopia, Ivory Coast and Singapore also showed increased mortality in patients presenting after 24 hours.^{21, 22, 23}

In addition, our study demonstrated a significant association between old age (>60 years), primary level of education and postoperative complications with mortality. These findings were consistent with similar studies conducted in South-western part of Nigeria, Tanzania and Ethiopia.^{6,8,21}

Charles *et al.* reported a decreasing in-patient mortality from 20% to 10.8% over a 15 year period in North of England.²⁴ This was attributed to early presentation, diagnosis and prompt management of their patients.

Limitations of the study

It was a single-center and retrospective study. Some of the patients had incomplete investigations such as serum albumin and inconsistent documentations that were not assessed in this study but could have altered the surgical outcome.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, perforated PUD is a life-threatening pathology with grave consequences in our environment even after surgical intervention. The major risk factor was chronic NSAID use among the youths. Late presentation and old age are factors contributing to poor outcome.

Conflict of interest: Nil

Source of Funding: Nil

Authors' Contribution; HOA and VG conceived and designed the study. HOA, VG, JTG and LBA all contributed to the conception and design of the study. HOA performed the statistical analysis with the assistance of a statistician. HOA, VG, JTG and LBA contributed to the interpretation of the findings and revision of the manuscript. All authors approved the final version of the article.

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